

LEARNING BY DESIGN

COGNITIVE AND EMOTIONAL FACTORS INFLUENCING INFORMAL LEARNING EXPERIENCES IN INTERACTIVE ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper offers an overview of a study synthesizing current literature in educational and design psychology, information design, human-computer interaction, and museum studies to identify cognitive and emotional factors that influence learning. The purpose is to produce a set of cognitive and emotional factors that museum educators, exhibit designers, information designers, and interaction designers should consider when designing informal learning experiences in interactive environments. Nine identified factor groups include affect, cognition, context, engagement, experiential learning, interactivity, narrative, self concepts, and usability.

Keywords: affect, cognition, engagement, experience design, experiential learning.

INTRODUCTION

Information experiences are changing and require a deeper understanding of human psychology and behavior in order to successfully address the needs of learners in interactive environments. This paper presents a set of factors that museum educators, exhibit designers, information designers, and interaction designers should consider when designing interactive learning environments. The paper is based on a study that identifies relevant factors in current literature, clusters them into factor groups, and provides an overview of how each fits into current academic research in a visual study results matrix (Leaper, 2011, Appendix A), showing emerging areas of overlap and omission between fields. This paper

offers an overview of the study intended to guide the creation of human-centered interactive learning environments.

According to the references selected for the study, design stakeholders should consider a range of interconnected, influential factors when designing informal learning experiences in interactive environments. These factors can be clustered into nine larger factor groups which include: *affect*, *cognition*, *context*, *engagement*, *experiential learning*, *interactivity*, *narrative*, *self concepts*, and *usability*. The factors identified in the study are interconnected and influence each other to produce experiences. As O'Brien and Toms (2010) suggest, "multiple factors of experience must be examined concurrently and are related to each other" and the "co-presence of multiple factors during experience will, in future, influence design guidelines" (p. 64). Designers and design stakeholders can consider the influential cognitive and emotional factors presented in order to create successful learning experiences in interactive environments

AFFECT

The affect factor group encompasses both *affect* itself (a response) and *affective quality* (stimulating a response) (Zhang & Li, 2005, p. 106). Although there are a number of similar terms, Norman (2002) uses the "reasonably neutral term 'affect'" to include "the concepts of affect, emotion, feelings, mood, motivation, and qualia" (p. 38). Affective quality can be described as "the ability of an object or stimulus to cause changes in one's affect" (Zhang & Li, 2005, p.

105). Notably, “objects, places, and events all have affective quality...[which enters] consciousness as they are affectively interpreted” (Zhang & Li, 2005, p. 106).

AFFECT AND HUMANS

Emotion is “the conscious experience of affect...[Humans] react emotionally to a situation before [they] access it cognitively” (Norman, 2004, p. 11). Subconscious experiences (such as affect) are “the most automatic, or fluent experiences” (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000, p. 421) and are inherent to meaningful human experiences since “positive emotions are critical to learning, curiosity, and creative thought” (Norman, 2004, p. 19). Affect makes humans “smart” (Norman, 2002, p. 39) by helping us judge experiences (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 432). Affinity is a personal (and judgmental) affective response; humans are “often drawn to a certain design with a natural attraction simply because of its aesthetics and beauty” (Jordan, 2010, p. 6). Affinity can be defined as:

The emotional connection someone feels for a product or service as driven by these notions of beauty and identity...affinity is about unexplained desire or want. It is often irrational, fluid, and intense. Affinity is the opposite of aversion, and affinity is always positive. (Jordan, 2010, p. 6)

Both positive and negative affect are important, for different reasons. A negative affective response “focuses the mind, leading to better concentration,” which is good for dangerous, high-pressure situations (Norman, 2002, p. 38), while “positive affect broadens the thought processes, making us more easily distracted” which is useful for creative problem-solving and low-pressure situations (Norman, 2002, p. 39).

AFFECT AND DESIGN

Because “the designed environment is the setting where our experiences take place and is impregnated with emotions” (Damazio et al., 2009, p. 2727), “understanding how and why things evoke emotions is...imperative to designing our environment” (Damazio et al., 2009, p. 2727). Interactions are “inevitably accompanied by affect” (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 435) and studies have shown affect to be “the single best predictor for the retrospective

product evaluation” (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 434). Hornecker et al. (2007) describe different reflexive affective responses occurring in different situations; they found a “pulling” motion results in positive attitude formation, and a “pushing” motion results in negative attitude formation (p. 336).

However, designing for affect and affinities can be “very challenging to include in a typical human-centered design approach” (Jordan, 2010, p. 8). Although recent attention has been given to the idea of experience design as a kind of theater where the participant plays a pre-orchestrated role, emotional experiences are more valuable when they are open-ended; Hennes (2002) notes that “pre-defining the outcome of experience is the goal of marketing; it is not the open-ended enrichment and pleasure that museums, at their best, can provide” (p. 110). In general, “pleasing things work better, are more regularly used, are easier to learn, influence future purchase choices, and produce a more harmonious result...thus affect and emotion have an important place in design” (Zhang & Li, 2005, p. 105). O’Brien and Toms (2010) describe “a more holistic representation of user engagement that indicates affect should be incorporated into interaction design and measurement” (p. 63).

AFFECT AND OTHER FACTORS

Affect is related to the *cognition, experiential learning, self concepts* and *usability* factor groups. Zhang and Li found that “a user’s immediate and reflexive affective reaction to [information technology (IT)] has a positive impact on his or her consequent cognition-oriented evaluations” (Zhang & Li, 2005, p. 107). Affect is crucial to learning because “positive affect arouses curiosity, engages creativity, and makes the brain into an effective learning organism” (Norman, 2004, p. 26). In fact, “the act of learning needs to be pleasurable in itself...if the interactor is to remain engaged” (Polaine, 2005, p. 154). Affect is related to self concepts because “the act of choosing and making decisions is intrinsically related to emotions” (Damazio et al., 2009, p. 2730). Affect and usability are inherently linked; “true beauty in a product has to be more than skin deep, more than a façade...good design means that beauty and usability are in balance” (Norman, 2002, p. 42). However, Zhang and Li (2005) note that “empirical evidence is scarce on

whether perceived affective quality of a system influences user perceptions of usefulness and ease of use of the system” and that in spite of “recent efforts to bring affect and emotion concepts into user acceptance studies, most of the existing studies are based on the assumption that human beings are rational and behave based on logical information-based thinking” (p. 106).

COGNITION

Cognition is defined by Norman (2002) as a neurological response that “interprets and makes sense of the world”; affect and cognition work together to help humans process information (p. 38). According to Richard Carlson’s (1997b) theory of experienced cognition, cognitive experience is the stream of incoming information perceived by humans during consciousness. Cognition can also be described as happening during interactions which “require us to think about what we are doing [and] require attention, cognitive effort, or problem-solving skills [sic]” (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000, p. 421).

COGNITION AND HUMANS

According to Forlizzi and Ford (2000), “experience [is the] constant stream that happens during moments of consciousness” (p. 419). Humans become aware of experience through self-talk and narration (Ibid). While “the affective system is judgmental, assigning positive and negative valence to the environment rapidly and efficiently...the cognitive system interprets and makes sense of the world” (Norman, 2002, p. 38). Hennes (2002) contrasts unconscious experience against interrupted experience, the latter being where “memory is formed and growth occurs” (p. 115). Allen suggests “immediate apprehendability,” defined as “the quality of a stimulus or larger environments such that people...will understand its purpose, scope, and properties almost immediately and without conscious effort,” can reduce cognitive load and make learning possible (Allen, 2004, p. S20). Van Moer et al. (2008) note that encouraging “engaging and assimilated experiences while creating capacities of critical thought and judgment...result[s] in the transformation of visitors’ attention into interest” (p. 44). Hennes (2002) discusses John Dewey’s concept of inquiry, which begins with a sense of unease or an intellectual

conflict and includes the following “steps” in inquiry cycle, which is different for every learner (p. 117-118):

- “interruption, obstruction, breaking the normal flow”
- “observations” and “inference” (a desire to understand the nature of the problem)
- “alternative solutions” (questioning multiple hypothesis)
- “reasoning” (testing and measuring)
- “verification” (resolving unease generated by conflict)

The process as a whole begins as activity halted by obstruction, moves through a process of thought and concludes again as activity restored. The difference between the activity of the beginning and that of the end is a kind of transformational growth that affects experience in the future. (Hennes, 2002, pp. 118-119).

COGNITION AND DESIGN

In order to create a “full cycle of inquiry,” museums should “promote reflection and inquiry [in] ways that are not simply ‘hands-on’” (Hein, 2004, p. 424). It is important to note “a content-based exhibit need not have a content-based form” (Hennes, 2002, p. 114) and can utilize observation, experimentation, problem solving, and pattern recognition. Hennes (2002) suggests “museums can offer experiences in which visitors participate in the formation of purposes driven by their own curiosity and interest” in order to create knowledge, rather than simply transfer it (p. 120). It is critical to “fashion engaging problems out of visitors’ own experience, through which visitors are motivated to draw upon the material resources of the exhibit in a desire for resolution” (Hennes, 2002, p. 116).

Van Moer et al. (2008) note “the challenge for museums is to find ways to formulate exhibitions that start from genuine experiences and lead to inquiry” (p. 50). Exhibition designers should “provide a cognitive map but not...predetermine the route” (Lake-Hammond & Waite, 2010, p. 80). In fact, “exhibits built around problematic situations may provide impetus for visitors to explore content in a way that is most meaningful to them because they take an active role in determining the purpose and the nature of the activity” (Hennes, 2002, p. 117). Not all learners require the same cognitive experience, however;

Renninger (2009) describes two phases of interest as it applies to learning:

In earlier phases of interest development, learners may be most likely to benefit from external supports (e.g., group work, meaningful content) that trigger and help to sustain their interests...In later phases of interest development, learners already have questions about the content and understand that work with the discipline involves open questions that will lead them to challenge their ideas. (p. 112)

COGNITION AND OTHER FACTORS

Cognition is related to the *affect*, *experiential learning*, and *usability* factor groups. According to Norman (2004) "emotion and cognition are thoroughly intertwined" (p. 8), since "cognition interprets and understands the world, while emotions allow you to make quick decisions" (p. 11). Renninger (2009) describes interest as "both a cognitive and affective motivational variable" (p. 106). A cognitive experience requires thought and "may offer a learning experience" (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000, p. 421). Recognizing and designing cognitive tools such as "natural mappings...limiting available controls, [and] standardizing for consistency" help users apprehend, which affects usability (Allen, 2004, p. S21).

CONTEXT

Although not always mentioned explicitly as an influential factor, many references imply that the context of a learning experience or interaction is critical to understanding its influences or outcome.

CONTEXT AND HUMANS

Dewey's notion of experience "has a beginning and an end, and changes the user, and sometimes, the context of the experience as a result" (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000, p. 420). Forlizzi and Ford (2000) note "user-product interactions take place in a context of use, shaped by social, cultural, and organizational behavior patterns" (Ibid). Social contexts are important too, because experiences and "artifacts do not exist outside of social relationships" (Damazio et al., 2009, p. 2733).

Context influences experience evaluation, which is especially dependent on whether the experience is goal (or task) oriented. Hazzenzahl and Ullrich (2007) identify two ways of evaluating experience: experiential (in the moment) and retrospective (after the fact) (p. 431). Experiential measures in the study include mental effort, affect, and spontaneity; retrospective measures are evaluation (judged as positive or negative) and knowledge acquisition (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 433). Hazzenzahl and Ullrich (2007) also identify two modes of experience: goal mode, where all activity is determined by pursuit of a goal, resulting in more mental effort and learning; and a more spontaneous action mode, where activity determines goals "on the fly" (p. 432). Results in this study show a "higher level of effort and better knowledge acquisition in the goal condition" (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 433). Interestingly, spontaneity results in positive affect for no-goal interactions, but negative affect for goal mode (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 436). In other words, a task (goal mode) makes users evaluate experience based on task fulfillment; in this case spontaneity becomes associated with more effort and negative affect. An absence of tasks (action mode) makes users evaluate a product (or experience) separately from learning or mental effort; in this case spontaneity is seen as positive (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007, p. 435).

CONTEXT AND DESIGN

Forlizzi and Ford (2000) discuss context in terms of shifts in the framework of use as important (p. 422). These include:

- Cognitive to subconscious shifts (learned experiences become automatic)
- Subconscious to cognitive (problem encountered; "can also signal that user is creating new knowledge, and that learning is taking place")
- Narrative to cognitive (re-examine established beliefs or processes)
- Subconscious/narrative to cognitive ("move user from the state of experience to having an experience...resulting in learning")
- Subconscious to storytelling (communicate experience)

- Narrative to storytelling (a formal process becomes personal through communication)

Hornecker et al. (2007) suggest museum protocol and organization, such as the implied idea of whether touch is acceptable, affects participant notion of “appropriate behaviors” (p. 340). In order to make museum experiences more accessible, Hein (2004) discusses “taking the museum to the community and the community to the museum” (p. 423). Museums should “formulate exhibitions that lead to inquiry and that guide visitors to apply the results of such inquiry to life situations” (Hein, 2004, p. 424). However, “the ability to relate the immediate outcomes of museum experiences back to life...remains a challenge” (Hein, 2004, p. 424). In terms of message context, museums have “become increasingly open to diverse interpretations of knowledge and more involved in sharing these with a variety of public audiences” (Lake-Hammond & Waite, 2010, p. 81).

CONTEXT AND OTHER FACTORS

Context influences all experiences, and therefore is related to all factors, but is of particular concern to creating learning experiences. According to Hein (2004), “all structured, specialized learning environments, whether formal (schools) or informal (museums), need to test their activities constantly against a criterion of their relation to the world outside the specialized setting” (p. 423). Museums “require integrated settings that foster discussion, challenge the learner, make connections to issues of interest to the learner, and provide guidance for application in the world outside the museum” (Ibid, p. 424).

ENGAGEMENT

O’Brien and Toms (2010) note that engagement is a loosely-defined concept, which is problematic because “without a consistent definition of engagement, it is difficult to ascertain that the systems we design and market are, in fact, engaging, or to identify what aspects of the interaction with technology engage or fail to engage users” (p. 50). Engagement is defined as being comprised of six interrelated factors that culminate in a user’s sense of durability: “Endurability was predicted by the other five factors...Aesthetics predicted Perceived Usability, Focused Attention, and Felt Involvement; Novelty

predicted Focused Attention and Felt Involvement” (Ibid, p. 62).

ENGAGEMENT AND HUMANS

O’Brien and Toms identified six factors “encompass[ing] the complex interaction between people and technology” which results in engagement (2010, p. 65). These factors of engagement are defined as: Focused Attention, Perceived Usability, Aesthetics, Endurability, Novelty, and Felt Involvement (Ibid, p. 62). Allen (2004) discusses Csikszentmihalyi’s idea that ideal learning in a museum is “driven by curiosity and interest then sustained by a flow state” (p. S23). Flow can be defined as being “fully involved with mind and body in an intrinsically motivated activity” (Ibid). Allen also discusses “Active Prolonged Engagement (APE),” which includes access to phenomena along with opportunities for deeper cognitive experiences (Ibid, p. S25). APE results in longer engagement times, elicits “driving questions” and includes physical interactions that vary in pattern and sequence (Ibid).

ENGAGEMENT AND DESIGN

A key to creating flow is matching challenge to skills, along with well-defined goals and rules (Allen, 2004, p. S23). According to Hennes (2002), “constructing activity with continuity of experience in mind demands that we find a way to provide visitors with a means of constructing the present experience out of what is already meaningful and important to them” (p. 113). This can be problematic in a museum environment since, “despite an expressed endorsement of visitor-focused experiences, exhibits in these institutions are largely shaped by pre-defined content rather than by experience itself” (Hennes, 2002, p. 110). This is unproductive because “information-based exhibits often create reactions without personal engagement and develop experiences not meaningful enough to capture visitors’ attention and open up to further growth” (Van Moer et al., 2008, p. 44).

ENGAGEMENT AND OTHER FACTORS

Engagement is related to the *affect*, *cognition*, and *self concepts* factor groups. According to O’Brien and Toms (2010), traditional ways of capturing data related to engagement “do not address the users’ cognitive or emotional state, both of which are critical

to engagement” (p. 52). For learning, “the most important thing is that tools should be developed to stimulate, improve, deepen and smooth the progress of visitors’ engagement in the inquiry cycle” (Van Moer et al., 2008, p. 50). The more engaged the participant, the more real learning occurs; knowledge transmission is not the same as being engaged, because “visitors’ attention is not transformed into interest” when “transmission of (factual) knowledge is achieved but understanding or engagement of thinking did not happen” (Van Moer et al., 2008, p. 46). Engagement is linked to self concepts because continuity of experience can result in engagement, therefore “constructing activity with continuity of experience in mind demands that we find a way to provide visitors with a means of constructing the present experience out of what is already meaningful and important to them” (Hennes, 2002, p. 113).

EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING

Experiential learning is the idea that humans create meaning from lived experience. Van Moer et al. suggest “visiting art museums is mainly about viewers making meaning of their experiences through interactions with artefacts [sic]” and note that “phrases such as ‘visitor-focused’ and ‘openended’ experiences, ‘process of making meaning’ and ‘experience as a basis for meaningmaking’ have roots in constructivist theory, hermeneutic philosophy and social semiotics” (p. 44).

EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING AND HUMANS

According to Hennes (2002), “an educative experience is valuable to the extent that it prepares one for broader, richer experiences in the future; it expands possibility”; in fact, “growth itself is both the means and the end” (p. 112). Museums have a mission to offer learning experiences; Hennes (2002) suggests rather than attempting to “impose their own priorities onto visitors, museums can harvest visitors’ priorities and offer ways of expanding them into richer purposes and interests” (p. 112). Exploration, physical manipulation, and experimentation help museum visitors learn (Allen, 2004, p. S19). Learning experiences are participatory rather than passive; Hornecker et al. (2007) suggest co-creation of ideas can lead to learning (p. 336). An inquiry cycle can be driven by curiosity (Allen, 2004, p. S20) and sustained

by engagement. It is interesting to note that comfort (both psychological and physical) is also a key factor for learning experiences (Allen, 2004, p. S24).

Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) suggests learning happens through a process of grasping concrete experiences and abstract concepts and transforming them through active experimentation or reflective observation (Kolb et al., 2001, p. 228). Human preferences for recognizing and integrating information are known as learning styles, which ELT categorizes as diverging, assimilating, converging, or accommodating (Kolb et al., 2001, pp. 229-231). Recently ELT has intersected with integrated learning theory, which conceives learning as a “spiral” of experiencing, reflecting, thinking, and acting in active response to a learning situation (Kolb et al., 2001, p. 240). The degree to which learners apply styles holistically is known as adaptive learning; sophisticated learners apply learning styles in all four areas in an “adaptively flexible” way (Kolb et al., 2001, p. 244).

It is especially notable that problematic experiences may lead to inquiry, and “disequilibrium” can be used as a driver for learning (Allen, 2004, p. S18). In fact, “experiences felt as obstacles for interpretation are extremely suitable to stimulate, deepen and improve visitors’ engagement in the inquiry cycle” (Van Moer et al., 2008, p. 43).

EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING AND DESIGN

Because “visitors vary in their preferences, styles and motivations for learning,” multimodal approaches, including multisensory experiences, can be used to apply universal design principles in order to create universally effective learning (Allen, 2004, p. S28). ELT, especially as it applies to adaptive learning, is of particular interest for interactive environments, which are inherently self-directed and can potentially serve a variety of learning styles simultaneously (Kolb et al., 2001). This is easier said than done; “institutions continue to have a difficult time persuading visitors to “learn” while they’re having their experiences” (Hennes, 2002, p. 110).

Designers can harness problematic experiences that initiate resolution of cognitive conflict in order to

encourage learning; Van Moer et al. (2008) describe Gooding-Brown's "disruptive model" based on problematic experience where multiple (and even conflicting) viewpoints are presented (p. 49). This suggests the participants create their own meaning through a resolution of conflicting opinions: "the basis for the disruptive model is found in the dilemma of authoritative interpretation and multiple voices' interpretation" (Ibid).

EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING AND OTHER FACTORS

Experiential learning is obviously connected with the *cognition* and *interactivity* factor groups, but also with the *engagement* factor group. The "learning process is one of the key elements of engagement" because humans want to become "better" at interactions (Polaine, 2005, p. 154).

INTERACTIVITY

According to Polaine (2005), "true interactivity is a feedback loop of action-reaction-interaction and involves collaboration or exchange" (p. 151).

INTERACTIVITY AND HUMANS

Sources identified by Birchfield et al. (2008) found "interactive media [and] active participation by visitors has been shown to increase audience attendance and appreciation in museum exhibits" (p. 965). This includes museums, since "exhibits are environments in which complex interactions occur among visitors, objects, environment, and meaning" (Hennes, 2002, p. 109).

Interactivity has a social component as well; shareability can be defined as "the extent that a system, interface, or device engages a group of collocated people in shared interactions around the same content (or object)" (Hornecker et al., 2007, p. 329). Fluidity of sharing affects "how easily people engaged in shared interactions" (Ibid, p. 336). Sharable interfaces mean "all group members can point to and manipulate shared content while simultaneously viewing the interactions and having a shared point of reference" (Hornecker et al., 2007, p. 329).

INTERACTIVITY AND DESIGN

According to Lake-Hammond and Waite (2010), "interaction design is particularly significant to

exhibition design in the way that it integrates visual communication and the design of material objects" (p. 88). Polaine (2005) notes that "the key to creating engaging interactivity is setting up the correct rules for a playful flow experience" (p. 153). Both "hands-on" and "minds-on" interactivity are important (Allen, 2004, p. S25). Familiar activities can be used as schemas: making a complex machine work; engaging in a competition; and watching and waiting, which is a surprisingly social activity (Allen, 2004, p. S22). Some interaction is key, but "exhibits may have an optimal degree of interactivity" (Allen, 2004, p. S25).

Entry and access are important aspects of interaction, because "offering a diversity of entry points enables different levels of engagement, allowing for gradual adoption and appropriation of a system" (Hornecker et al., 2007, p. 332). Shared interactions cause a visual draw to access points, creating a "honeypot effect" that encourages use (Ibid). According to Hornecker et al. (2007), "entry points invite people and entice them to interact with the system or product" (p. 331), and entry points differ by:

- intrusiveness (attention-drawing)
- richness (amount of information and memory triggers)
- visibility (how perceptible)
- freshness (newness/last use)

Designers should note that "the number and location of access points are important, as too is simultaneous access, which can distribute control in a group" (Hornecker et al., 2007, p. 334). In terms of information experiences, Hennes (2002) suggests creating "entry points into a body of intellectual content" (p. 113), such as:

- analogies (using everyday examples)
- breaking a subject into units that reference participants' prior experience

INTERACTIVITY AND OTHER FACTORS

Interactivity is related to the *engagement*, *experiential learning*, and *narrative* factor groups. Polaine (2005) discusses the immersive quality of interactivity as being similar to conventional narratives:

Conventional narratives attempt to mask the structure of the story (plot, characterisation,

dramatic turning points) by using that very structure to create emotional hooks on which to hang our disbelief. When the structure starts to crumble we become aware of the printed page or the fact that we are in the cinema and we start to withdraw from the world of the story. This is often because the fine-tuning has gone astray; perhaps a typographic error, an unconvincing visual effect or an infeasible coincidence. When we find an interactive [element or] interface confusing and frustrating (and it is not deliberate) we have a similar experience; we are jettisoned back into real-world emotions and removed from those that we were experiencing in the represented world. (p. 153)

Social aspects of interactions are important to learning because “exhibitions that allow for multiple simultaneous users facilitate family learning” (Allen, 2004, p. S26). Birchfield et al. (2008) note that “constructivist learning [emphasizes] play and exploration in self-guided learning” situations (p. 966). Hands-on learning creates “an increase in motivation and engagement” with “younger visitors more willing to interact” (Ibid, p. 968).

NARRATIVE

In terms of exhibition design, narrative can be defined as a structure that “allows the audience to make sense of the objects on display, in relation to one another and their surrounding contexts” (Lake-Hammond & Waite, 2010, p. 91).

NARRATIVE AND HUMANS

Narratives are the stories that create meaning from experiences. Forlizzi and Ford (2000) discuss Roger Shank’s idea of experience as story, explaining “stories are the vehicles that we use to condense and remember experiences, and to communicate them” (p. 420). Forlizzi and Ford (2000) “use the word narrative to represent experiences that have been formalized in the user’s head...or in the world,” such as product features (p. 422). They use storytelling to define “the subjective aspects of experience,” including context of use and subjective qualities such as emotion, to create “a unique and subjective story” (Ibid). According to Lake-Hammond and Waite (2010):

A strong narrative enables the visitor to discover the exhibition’s complete meaning, rather than viewing it as a series of separate entities. Narrative structure does not need to be explicit or complex. In fact, a subtle narrative tends to be more successful, allowing audiences access to the exhibition message without distracting them with excess information. (p. 92)

NARRATIVE AND DESIGN

“Personal storytelling” can be an effective learning tool, but needs to be better understood in order to “harness narrative in the service of helping visitors understand exhibits” (Allen, 2004, p. S29). Since “a coherent exhibition narrative [can] provide the audience with the necessary structure to formulate meaning,” it is important to consider narrative from a participant perspective (Lake-Hammond & Waite, 2010, p. 91):

The audience then is an active participant in the exhibition narrative. The design does not directly tell the audience a story, but implies that one exists, encouraging each individual visitor to interpret the exhibition concept and develop their own understandings. It is important that the designer recognizes that no two visitors will engage in the narrative in the same way. (Ibid, p. 92)

NARRATIVE AND OTHER FACTORS

Narrative is related to the *affect* and *context* factor groups. Forlizzi and Ford (2000) use storytelling to define “the subjective aspects of experience,” including context of use and subjective qualities such as emotion, to create “a unique and subjective story” (p. 422).

SELF CONCEPTS

The self concepts factor group includes factors concerned with identity and self.

SELF CONCEPTS AND HUMANS

Designed experiences are inherently tied to the self, since “identity, like interest, develops through interactions...both interest and identity develop in relation to available experiences and to how learners perceive, understand, and represent these

experiences” (Renninger, 2009, p. 106). Damazio et al. (2009) discuss product experiences as co-authored, creating in a sense of self-ownership, since “to appreciate an object is a way of participating in its creation” (p. 2729). According to Jordan (2010):

A design has the ability to take me back to a place, time, or experience to which I would like to return; it can allow me to be part of a community and can help define me in relation to others in a group; and it can even help me signify who I want to become. (p. 11)

Identifying closely with an experience can create an affinity, which is tied into a sense of self:

Affinities based on self-image...may be nostalgic (past tense) and relate to who we thought we were or a fondness we have for past experiences. It can also be definitive (present tense) and help us communicate who we are and to which community we belong. And affinity may even be aspirational (future tense) and allow us to project who we want to be and our ideals for our future. (Jordan, 2010, p. 8)

SELF CONCEPTS AND DESIGN

Understanding participants and their ideas of self is critical, because “information about interest and identity development could usefully inform the design of tasks, exhibits, and activities; instructional conversations; and expectations for learner participation and achievement” (Renninger, 2009, p. 105). Shared authorship, co-authorship, and “design in partnership” can be explained as “designing ‘with’ as opposed to ‘for’ people,” and includes “collaboration between designers and future users” (Damazio et al., 2009, p. 2729). This participatory and inclusive approach is important for museums because “museums should grow out of life experiences and be used to reflect back on life” (Hein, 2004, p. 420). In order to create personal meaning, “museum experiences, even active ones, still need to be associated with richer, authentic life experiences” (Hein, 2004, p. 423). This implies an important and relatively newly-acknowledged significance for design:

“bridging the gap between growing expert knowledge and satisfying an increasing desire for democratic participation in its dissemination can be seen as an important cultural role

for design” (Lake-Hammond & Waite, 2010, p. 88).

SELF CONCEPTS AND OTHER FACTORS

Self concepts are related to the *affect* factor group because affinity is comprised of an emotional response to beauty and identity, and “identity may be best explored in terms of the self image” (Jordan, 2010, p. 6). The amount of effort and self-investment in an experience can determine affective response, since “the effort exerted in the acquisition of an object is one of the aspects responsible for the feeling of independence that can be generated by the relationship of people with their objects” (Damazio et al., 2009, p. 2730).

USABILITY

Usability can be described as the practice of designing for ease of use, a field rooted in “cognitive sciences—a combination of psychology, computer science, human factors, and engineering” (Norman, 2002, p. 38). *Usability* derives from *userfriendly*, but “no precise definition of usability exists” (Alonso-Ríos et al., 2010, p. 53); many researchers rely on international standards (ISO) definitions (Ibid, p. 54).

USABILITY AND HUMANS

User-centered design can be described as an approach that promotes “the creation of objects that, by virtue of their physical forms and location invite certain kinds of use and not others,” including the notion of “affordances” or interactions where intended use is natural and apparent (Allen, 2004, p. S21). Alonso-Ríos et al. (2010) found six areas that pertain to usability: knowability, operability, efficiency, robustness, safety, and subjective satisfaction (p. 60).

USABILITY AND DESIGN

According to Forlizzi and Ford (2000), “a successful design will take into consideration all the components in the user-product interaction: user, product, and context of use” (p. 423). It’s not enough to simply acknowledge the importance of usability; a more concrete and systematic approach is necessary because “designers need to demystify how we design for user experience and how the products we design achieve specific user experience goals” (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000, p. 419). According to Norman (2002),

“human-centered design practices are most essential for tasks or situations that are stressful” since people can tolerate less-user friendly interactions in pleasant situations (p. 40). Usability is critical to museum experiences because a decline in interest and involvement known as museum fatigue can set in after about 30 minutes (Allen, 2004, p. S20).

USABILITY AND OTHER FACTORS

Usability is related to the *cognition*, *affect*, and *context* factor groups. Apprehension and usability “reduce the ever-present cognitive load on visitors, freeing them to focus on those aspects of the environment that are rewarding to them and worthy of their attention” (Allen, 2004, p. S24). O’Brien and Toms suggest “aesthetic judgments are not based solely on users’ first impressions; the perceived usability of a system is intertwined with its visual presentation” (2010, p. 63). According to Zhang and Li (2005), “IT designers or IT acquirers should pay attention not only to usefulness (IT suitability for tasks or jobs), and ease of use (the longtime goal of the human computer interaction field), but also to affective quality (the degree to which emotional reactions are evoked)” (p. 108). Context is a hugely important factor to determine what “usability” means in a given situation, hence “usability depends on context of use” (Alonso-Ríos et al., 2010, p. 60).

CONCLUSION

Information experiences are changing and require a deeper understanding of human psychology and behavior in order to successfully address the needs of learners in interactive environments. According to Lake-Hammond and Waite (2010), “an exhibition curator is still responsible for the collection and research of the exhibition’s content, but increasingly draws on the interpretive abilities of communication designers to ensure that the exhibition audience can access, interact with, and form their own interpretations of the exhibition’s message” (p. 81). The outcome of this study presents a set of factors that museum educators, exhibit designers, information designers, and interaction designers should consider when designing interactive learning environments.

According to the references selected for this study, design stakeholders should consider a range of interconnected, influential factors when designing

informal learning experiences in interactive learning environments. These factors can be clustered into nine larger factor groups which include: *affect*, *cognition*, *context*, *engagement*, *experiential learning*, *interactivity*, *narrative*, *self concepts*, and *usability*. The factors identified in this study are interconnected and influence each other to produce experiences. As O’Brien and Toms (2010) suggest, “multiple factors of experience must be examined concurrently and are related to each other” and the “co-presence of multiple factors during experience will, in future, influence design guidelines” (p. 64). Designers and design stakeholders can consider the influential cognitive and emotional factors presented in order to create successful learning experiences in interactive environments.

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